

1 **Control of Ly6K by HPV E6.**

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6 We measured total transcription in cells over-expressing the papillomavirus E6 gene that has described
7 functions in binding and inactivation of p53 for discovery of novel E6 associated cellular functions. We
8 demonstrate here control of Ly6K by HPV E6. This was a conserved property of HPV E6 across type: for
9 both HPV16 E6 and for HPV84 E6.

10 Citations

11 1. Luo, L., McGarvey, P., Madhavan, S., Kumar, R., Gusev, Y. and Upadhyay, G., 2016. Distinct
12 lymphocyte antigens 6 (Ly6) family members Ly6D, Ly6E, Ly6K and Ly6H drive tumorigenesis and clinical
13 outcome. *Oncotarget*, 7(10), p.11165.

14 GSE228187